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REVIEW ON ASTANGA - NIGHANTU

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Abstract

Nighantu is one of the important aspects in the study of *Dravyaguna Vijnana*. The *Nighantu* literature is one of the significant facets in the study of Ayurveda and especially in the subject of *Dravyaguna Vijnana*. In the tradition of Ayurvedic *Nighantu*, *Astanga Nighantu* is one of the important *Nighantu*. This work is of medieval period. In order to understand the *Samhitagrantha* easily, there has been a tradition of composing the *Nighantugrantha*. In the same series, we get the *Astanga-Nighantu* related to *Astanga-hrdaya*. *Astanga-Nighantu* is an ancient text of the Ayurvedic *Nighantu* tradition composed by synonymous style. It consists of 27 *Gana*. The objective of this review is to analyse the importance and utility of *Astanga-hrdaya*.

Key Words:

Ayurveda, *Astanga Nighantus*, *Dravyaguna*, *Nighantu*

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INTRODUCTION:

The term 'Nigama' is the basis for the word *Nighantu*. The term "Nigama" has an etymology that reveals words deeply hidden or secret meanings.¹ The essential medications of *Astangahridaya* are compiled in *Astanga Nighantu*, written by *Vagbhata*. Synonyms of medicinal substances discussed in related *Samhita* are compiled in these *Astanga Nighantus*.² The manuscripts are available in South India. In the available manuscripts, it has been described as a creation of *Vagbhata*. It has been stated that two manuscripts of *Astanga Nighantus* are mentioned in the descriptive catalogue of manuscripts of the Government Oriental Manuscripts Library, Chennai. One with Telugu meaning and the other with Tamil meaning.³

Time period of *Astanga Nighantus*:

The approximate composing period of this *Nighantu* should be around the 8th century AD. *Astanga Nighantus* is of medieval period. The majority of literature on *Nighantu* were produced during this period.⁴

Table No.:1 Contents of *Astanga Nighantu*⁵:

The order of the contents of the work are:

1.	<i>Dravyas of 26 Gana of Vagbhata</i>	14.	<i>IksuVarga and Madhu Varga</i>
2.	Other plant drugs	15.	<i>Taila Varga</i>
3.	Plants belonging to <i>Saka Varga</i>	16.	<i>Madya Varga</i>
4.	Plants belonging to <i>Phala Varga</i>	17.	<i>Dhanya Varga</i>
5.	<i>Parthiva Dravya</i>	18.	<i>Mishra Varga</i>
6.	<i>Lavana and Kshara</i>	19.	<i>Krtanna Varga</i>
7.	<i>Jantava Dravyas</i>	20.	<i>Anga Pratyaya</i>
8.	<i>Gandha Dravya</i>	21.	<i>Mamsa Varga</i>
9.	<i>Dhatu</i>	22.	<i>Sarira Dhatus and Dosas</i>

10.	<i>Visa</i>	23.	Earth and Planets
11.	<i>Jaliya Dravyas</i>	24.	Gods and Goddesses
12.	<i>Puspa Varga</i>	25.	Parts of plants
13.	<i>Dravya Varga</i>	26.	Medicine and physician

Gana: There is total 26 *Gana* in *Astanga Nighantu*. They are⁶:

Table No. 2: List of 27 *Gana* described in *Astanga Nighantu*

1.	<i>Vidaryadiganah</i>	15.	<i>Arkadiganah</i>
2.	<i>Sarivadiganah</i>	16.	<i>Surasadiganah</i>
3.	<i>Pippalyadiganah</i>	17.	<i>Muskakadiganah</i>
4.	<i>Padmakadiganah</i>	18.	<i>Vatsakadiganah</i>
5.	<i>Parusakadiganah</i>	19.	<i>Vacadiganah</i>
6.	<i>Anjanadiganah</i>	20.	<i>Haridradiganah</i>
7.	<i>Patoladiganah</i>	21.	<i>Priyangvadiganah</i>
8.	<i>Guducyadiganah</i>	22.	<i>Ambasthadiganah</i>
9.	<i>Aragvadhadiganah</i>	23.	<i>Mustadiganah</i>
10.	<i>Asanadiganah</i>	24.	<i>Nyagrodhadiganah</i>
11.	<i>Varunadiganah</i>	25.	<i>Eladiganah</i>
12.	<i>Usakadiganah</i>	26.	<i>Syamadiganah</i>
13.	<i>Virataradiganah</i>	27.	<i>Viprakirnadravyani</i>
14.	<i>Rodhradiganah</i>	28.	<i>Arkadiganah</i>

1). Vidaryadiganah:

Dravya of *Vidaryadiganah* are useful in *Shosh, Gulma, Angamarda, Shwas, Kasa, Bruhana, Hrudya*, It has total of 21 *Dravya*. They are⁷:

Table No. (3) List of Dravya described in *Vidaryadi Gana*

Sanskrit name	Latin / English name	Sanskrit name	Latin / English name
<i>Vidari</i>	<i>Pueraria tuberosa</i>	<i>Eranda</i>	<i>Ricinus communis</i>
<i>Vrscikali</i>	<i>Tragia involucrata</i>	<i>Punarnava</i>	<i>Boerhavia diffusa</i>
<i>Sahadeva</i>	<i>Vernonia cinerea</i>	<i>Nagabala</i>	<i>Grewia hirsute</i>
<i>Mudgaparni</i>	<i>Vigna trilobata</i>	<i>Masaparni</i>	<i>Teramnus labialis</i>
<i>Kapikacchu</i>	<i>Mucuna pruriens</i>	<i>Satavari</i>	<i>Asparagus racemosus Willd</i>
<i>Kakoli</i>	<i>Roscoeia procera</i>	<i>Jivanti</i>	<i>Leptadenia reticulata</i>
<i>Jivaka</i>	<i>Crepidium acuminatum</i>	<i>Prishnaparni</i>	<i>Uraria picta</i>
<i>Salaparni</i>	<i>Desmodium gangeticum</i>	<i>Kantakari</i>	<i>Solanum virginianum</i>
<i>Vartaki</i>	<i>Solanum anguivi</i>	<i>Goksura</i>	<i>Tribulus terrestris</i>
<i>Sariva</i>	<i>Hemidesmus indicus</i>	<i>Hamsapadi</i>	<i>Adiantum philippense</i>
<i>Rusabhaka</i>	<i>Malaxis muscifera</i>		

2). Sarivadigana:

Dravya of *Sarivadiganah* are useful in *Daha, Pittavyadhi, Raktaroga, Trushna, Jwara*. It has total of 8 *Dravya*. They are⁸:

Table No. (4) List of Dravya described in *Sarivadi Gana*

Sanskrit name	Latin / English name	Sanskrit name	Latin / English name
<i>Sariva</i>	<i>Hemidesmus indicus</i>	<i>Usira</i>	<i>Vetiveria zizanioides</i>

<i>Kasmarya</i>	<i>Gmelina arborea</i>	<i>Madhuka</i>	<i>Madhuca longifolia</i>
<i>Svetachandana</i>	<i>Santalum album L.</i>	<i>Raktachandana</i>	<i>Pterocarpus Santalinus</i> <i>L.f.</i>
<i>Madhuyasti</i>	<i>Glycyrrhiza glabra</i>	<i>Parusaka</i>	<i>Grewia asiatica</i>

3). Pippalyadigana:

Dravya of Pippalyadigana are useful in *Kaphaj Vyadhi*. It has total of 23 *Dravya*. They are⁹:

Table No. (5) List of *Dravya* described in *Pippalyadi gana*

Sanskrit name	Latin / English name	Sanskrit name	Latin / English name
<i>Pippali</i>	<i>Piper longum L.</i>	<i>Pippalimula</i>	<i>Piper longum</i>
<i>Kakamachi</i>	<i>Solanum americanum Mill.</i>	<i>Chavya</i>	<i>Piper retrofractum</i>
<i>Sunthi</i>	<i>Zingiber officinale</i>	<i>Jiraka</i>	<i>Cuminum cyminum L.</i>
<i>Krusnajira</i>	<i>Carum carvi L.</i>	<i>Upakuncika</i>	<i>Nigella sativa</i>
<i>Patha</i>	<i>Cissampelos pareira</i>	<i>Hingu</i>	<i>Ferula narthex Boiss</i>
<i>Renuka</i>	<i>Vitex agnus-castus</i>	<i>Gajapippali</i>	<i>Piper retrofractum</i>
<i>Rajika</i>	<i>Brassica juncea</i>	<i>Svetasarsapa</i>	<i>Sinapis alba L.</i>
<i>Katuka</i>	<i>Picrorhiza kurroa</i>	<i>Maricha</i>	<i>Piper nigrum L.</i>
<i>Sprukka</i>	<i>Anisomeles malabarica</i>	<i>Jatiphala</i>	<i>Myristica fragrans</i>
<i>Ajamoda</i>	<i>Apium graveolens</i>	<i>Ela</i>	<i>Elettaria cardamomum (L.)</i>
<i>Bharngi</i>	<i>Clerodendrum serratum(L)</i>		

4). Padmakadigana:

Dravya of *Padmakadigana* are useful for *Stanyakara*, *Preenana*, *Jivana*, *Bruhan*, *Vrusya*. It has total of 17 *Dravya*. They are¹⁰:

Table No. (6) List of Dravya described in *Padmakadi gana*

Sanskrit name	Latin / English name	Sanskrit name	Latin / English name
<i>Hemapadma</i>	<i>Prunus cerasoides</i>	<i>Prapaundarika</i>	-
<i>Vruddhi</i>	<i>Habenaria intermedia</i>	<i>Mahavruddhi</i>	<i>Habenaria edgeworthii Hook.F.</i>
<i>Vamsarochana</i>	<i>Bambusa bambos</i>	<i>Srungi</i>	<i>Pistacia chinensis</i>
<i>Guduchi</i>	<i>Tinospora cordifolia</i>		

The 10 drugs of *jivaniyagana* are already being described earlier. *Jivanti*, *Kakoli*, *Kshirakakoli*, *Mahameda*, *Meda*, *Mudgaparni*, *masaparni*, *jivaka*, *rsabhaka*, *madhuyasti*.

Meda,

5). Parusakadiganah:

Dravya of *Parusakadiganah* are useful for *Trusna*, *Mutraamaya*, *Vataroga*. It has total of 10 *Dravya*. They are¹¹:

Table No. (7) List of Dravya described in *Parusakadiganah*

Sanskrit name	Latin / English name	Sanskrit name	Latin / English name
<i>Parusaka</i>	<i>Grewia asiatica</i>	<i>Bibhitaka</i>	<i>Terminalia bellirica</i>
<i>Amalaki</i>	<i>Phyllanthus emblica</i>	<i>Draksha</i>	<i>Vitis conifers L.</i>
<i>Katphala</i>	<i>Myrica esculenta</i>	<i>Kataka</i>	<i>Strychnos potatorum L.f.</i>
<i>Rajadana</i>	<i>Manilkara hexandra</i>	<i>Dadima</i>	<i>Punica granatum</i>
<i>Sakavruksha</i>	<i>Tectona grandis</i>	<i>Haritaki</i>	<i>Terminalia chebula</i>

6). Anjanadiganah:

Dravya of **Anjanadiganah** are useful in *Visha, Pittaroga, Antadaha*. It has total of 9 *Dravya*. They are¹²:

Table No. (8) List of Dravya described in Anjanadiganah

Sanskrit name	Latin / English name	Sanskrit name	Latin / English name
<i>Srotonjan</i>	-	<i>Sauviranjana</i>	-
<i>Priyangu</i>	<i>Callicarpa macrophylla Vahl</i>	<i>Mamsi</i>	<i>Nardostachys jatamansi</i>
<i>Padma</i>	<i>Nelumbo nucifera</i>	<i>Nilotpala</i>	<i>Nymphaea nouchali</i>
<i>Raktotpala</i>	<i>Nymphaea tubes Roxb.</i>	<i>Rasanjana</i>	<i>Elettaria cardamomum</i>
<i>Nagakeshara</i>	<i>Mesua ferrea</i>		

7). Patoladiganah

Dravya of **Patoladiganah** are useful for *Kushta, Jwar, Visha, Arochaka, Kamala*. It has total of 6 *Dravya*. They are¹³:

Table No. (9) List of Dravya described in Patoladiganah

Sanskrit name	Latin / English name	Sanskrit name	Latin / English name
<i>Patola</i>	<i>Trichosanthes dioica</i>	<i>Patha</i>	<i>Cissampelos pareira</i>
<i>Katurohini</i>	<i>Picrorhiza kurroa</i>	<i>Chandana</i>	<i>Pterocarpus Santalinus L.f.</i>
<i>Madhusrava</i>	-	<i>Guduchi</i>	<i>Tinospora cordifolia</i>

8). Guducyadiganah

Dravya of **Guducyadiganah** are useful for *Jwar, Chardi, Daha, Trushna*. It has total of 5 *Dravya*. They are¹⁴:

Table No. (10) List of Dravya described in *Guducyadiganah*

Sanskrit name	Latin / English name	Sanskrit name	Latin / English name
<i>Guduchi</i>	<i>Tinospora cordifolia</i>	<i>Padmaka</i>	<i>Prunus cerasoides</i>
<i>Nimba</i>	<i>Azadirachta indica</i>	<i>Dhanyaka</i>	<i>Coriandrum sativum L.</i>
<i>Raktachandana</i>	<i>Pterocarpus Santalinus L.f.</i>		

9). *Aragvadhiganah*

Dravya of *Aragvadhiganah* are useful for *Chardi, Visha, Jwar, Kandu, Prameha, Dushtavrana*. It has total of 20 *Dravya*. They are 15:

Table No. (11) List of *Dravya* described in *Aragvadhiganah*

Sanskrit name	Latin / English name	Sanskrit name	Latin / English name
<i>Aragvadha</i>	<i>Cassia fistula</i>	<i>Indrayava</i>	<i>Holarrhena antidysenterica L.</i>
<i>Patala</i>	<i>Stereospermum chelonoides</i>	<i>Kakatika</i>	
<i>Vikankata</i>	<i>Flacourtia indica</i>	<i>Bhunimba</i>	<i>Swertia chirayita</i>
<i>Sairyaka</i>	<i>Barleria prionitis</i>	<i>Karanja</i>	<i>Pongamia pinnata</i>
<i>Putikaranja</i>	<i>Holoptelea integrifolia</i>	<i>Saptacchada</i>	<i>Alstonia scholaris</i>
<i>Chitraka</i>	<i>Plumbago zeylanica</i>	<i>Raktachitraka</i>	<i>Plumbago indica</i>
<i>Susavi</i>	-	<i>Madana</i>	<i>Xeromphis spinosa</i>
<i>Ghonta</i>	<i>Ziziphus xylopyra</i>	<i>Nimba</i>	<i>Azadirachta indica</i>
<i>Guduchi</i>	<i>Tinospora cordifolia</i>	<i>Madhurasa</i>	<i>Marsdenia tenacissima</i>

10). Asanadigahah

Dravya of **Asanadigaha** are useful for *Shwitra, Kushta, Krumi, Pandu, Prameha, Medoroga*. It has total of 23 *Dravya*. They are¹⁶:

Table No. (12) List of Dravya described in Asanadigahah

Sanskrit name	Latin / English name	Sanskrit name	Latin / English name
<i>Asana</i>	<i>Pterocarpus marsupium</i> <i>Roxb.</i>	<i>Tinisa</i>	<i>Ougeinia oojeinensis</i>
<i>Bhurja</i>	<i>Betula utilis</i> D.Don	<i>Arjuna</i>	<i>Terminalia arjuna</i>
<i>Khadira</i>	<i>Acacia catechu</i>	<i>Kadara</i>	<i>Acacia polyacantha</i>
<i>Sirisa</i>	<i>Albizia lebeck</i> L.	<i>Simsapa</i>	<i>Dalbergia sissoo</i>
<i>Mesarsngi</i>	<i>Gymnema sylvestre</i>	<i>Kaleyaka</i>	<i>Coscinium fenestratum</i>
<i>Tala</i>	<i>Borassus flabellifer</i>	<i>Palasa</i>	<i>Butea monosperm</i>
<i>Agaru</i>	<i>Aquilaria malaccensis</i>	<i>Salavrksa</i>	<i>Shorea robusta</i> Gaertn
<i>Dhava</i>	<i>Anogeissus latifolia</i>	<i>Kramuka</i>	<i>Areca catechu</i> L.
<i>Ajakarna</i>	<i>Vateria indica</i> L.	<i>Asvakarna</i>	<i>Dipterocarpus turbinatus</i>
<i>Prakirya</i>	-	<i>Trihima</i>	-
<i>Raktachandan</i>	<i>Pterocarpus Santalinus</i> L.f	<i>Pittachandana</i>	-
<i>Saka</i>	-	<i>Kalinga</i>	<i>Holarrhena antidysenterica</i> L.

11). Varunadiganah

Dravya of **Varunadiganah** are useful for *Aathayavata, Shirshoola, Gulma, Vidradhi*. It has total of 14 *Dravya*. They are¹⁷:

Table No. (13) List of Dravya described in *Varunadiganah*

Sanskrit name	Latin / English name	Sanskrit name	Latin / English name
<i>Varuna</i>	<i>Crataeva nurvala</i>	<i>Bilva</i>	<i>Aegle marmelos(L.)</i>
<i>Rakta Sairyaka</i>	-	<i>Pita Sairyaka</i>	-
<i>Satavari</i>	<i>Asparagus racemosus Willd</i>	<i>Dahana (Chitraka)</i>	<i>Plumbago zeylanica</i>
<i>Morata</i>	-	<i>Bilva</i>	<i>Aegle marmelos(L.)</i>
<i>Bruhati</i>	<i>Solanum indicum Linn.</i>	<i>Kantakari</i>	<i>Solanum virginianum</i>
<i>Tarkari haritaki</i>	-	<i>Karanjaadvaya</i>	<i>Pongamia pinnata</i>
<i>Ajasrangi</i>	-	<i>Arani</i>	<i>Premna serratifolia</i>
<i>Sigru</i>	<i>Moringa oleifera</i>	<i>Madhusigru</i>	<i>Moringa concanensis</i>
<i>Darbha</i>	<i>Imperata cylindrica</i>	<i>Artagala</i>	<i>Xanthium strumarim</i>

12). *Usakadiganah*

Dravya of *Usakadigana* are useful for *Gulma*, *Medaroga*, *Ashmari*, *Mutrakruchha*. It has total of 7 *Dravya*. They are¹⁸:

Table No. (14) List of Dravya described in *Usakadiganah*

Sanskrit name	Latin / English name	Sanskrit name	Latin / English name
<i>Usaka</i>	<i>Dorema ammoniacum</i>	<i>Tutthaka</i>	-
<i>Hingu</i>	<i>Ferula narthex Boiss.</i>	<i>Puspakasisa</i>	-

<i>Saindhavalavana</i>	-	<i>Silajatu</i>	-
<i>Pamsudhatu</i>	-		

13). *Virataradiganah*

Dravya of *Virataradigana* are useful for *Ashmari*, *Sharkara*, *Mutrakruchcha*, *Rujahara*. It has total of 21 *Dravya*. They are¹⁹:

Table No. (15) List of *Dravya* described in *Virataradiganah*

Sanskrit name	Latin / English name	Sanskrit name	Latin / English name
<i>Virataru</i>	<i>Dichrostachys cinerea</i>	<i>Buka</i>	<i>Osmanthus fragrans</i>
<i>Vasa</i>	<i>Adhatoda zeylanica</i>	<i>Venuptari</i>	-
<i>Vrusa</i>	-	<i>Gokantaka</i>	-
<i>Pasanabheda</i>	<i>Bergenia ciliata</i>	<i>Utkata</i>	-
<i>Bana</i>	<i>Saccharum bengalense Retz.</i>	<i>Kasa</i>	<i>Saccharum spontaneum</i>
<i>Vandaka</i>	<i>Dendrophthoe falcata</i>	<i>Nala</i>	<i>Phragmites karka</i>
<i>Guntha</i>	<i>Typha australis</i>	<i>Tuntuka</i>	<i>Oroxylum Indicom L.</i>
<i>Kurantaka</i>	<i>Celosia argentea</i>	<i>Karambha</i>	<i>Pergularia daemia</i>
<i>Kapotavanka</i>	-	<i>Aranika</i>	-
<i>Sahachara</i>	-	<i>Gundra</i>	-
<i>Morata</i>	-		

14). *Rodhradiganah*

Dravya of *Rodhradigana* are useful for *Yonidosahara*, *Varnya*, *Visha*. It has total of 13 *Dravya*. They are²⁰:

Table No. (16) List of *Dravya* described in *Rodhradiganah*

Sanskrit name	Latin / English name	Sanskrit name	Latin / English name
<i>Lodhra</i>	<i>Symplocos racemosa Roxb.</i>	<i>Sabaralodhra</i>	<i>Symplocos paniculata</i>
<i>Jhingini</i>	<i>Lannea coromandelica</i>	<i>Sarala</i>	<i>Pinus roxburghii</i>

<i>Rasna</i>	<i>Pluchea lanceolata</i>	<i>Kadamba</i>	<i>Anthocephalus cadamba</i>
<i>Kadali</i>	<i>Musa paradisiaca</i>	<i>Ashoka</i>	<i>Saraca indica</i>
<i>Elavaluka</i>	<i>Prunus cerasus</i>	<i>Paripelava</i>	<i>Cyperus platyphyllus</i>
<i>Shallaki</i>	<i>Bosxellia serrata Roxb.</i>	<i>Palasa</i>	<i>Butea monosperma</i>
<i>Katphala</i>			

15). Arkadiganah

Dravya of **Arkadiganah** are useful for *Krumi, Kushta, Kapharoga, Medoroga, Visha*. It has total of 14 *Dravya*. They are²¹:

Table No. (17) List of *Dravya* described in *Arkadiganah*

Sanskrit name	Latin / English name	Sanskrit name	Latin / English name
<i>Arka</i>	<i>Calotropis procera</i>	<i>Alarka</i>	<i>Calotropis gigantea</i>
<i>Nagadanti</i>	<i>Croton oblongifolius</i>	<i>Langali</i>	<i>Gloriosa superba</i>
<i>Bharngi</i>	<i>Clerodendrum serratum</i>	<i>Apamarga</i>	<i>Achyranthes aspera</i>
<i>Jyotishmati</i>	<i>Celastrus paniculatus</i>	<i>Sveta (kinihi)</i>	-
<i>Mahasveta</i>	-	<i>Vandhyakarkotaki(kumari)</i>	-
<i>Inguda</i>	<i>Balanites aegyptiaca</i>	<i>Rasana</i>	<i>Pluchea lanceolata</i>
<i>Vruschikali</i>	-	<i>Prakirya</i>	<i>Pluchea lanceolata</i>

16). Surasadiganah

Dravyas of **Surasadiganah** are useful for *Pratishyay, Aruchi, Shwas, Kasa, Vranasodhana, Krumi, Medoroga*. It has total of 20 *Dravya*. They are²²:

Table No. (18) List of Dravya described in *Surasadiganah*

Sanskrit name	Latin / English name	Sanskrit name	Latin / English name
<i>Surasa (Sveta tulasi)</i>	<i>Ocimum sanctum L.</i>	<i>Krsna tulasi</i>	-
<i>Kathinjara</i>	<i>Orthosiphon aristatus</i>	<i>Vidanga</i>	<i>Embelia ribes Burm.f.</i>
<i>Marubaka</i>	<i>Origanum majorana</i>	<i>Akhukarni</i>	<i>Merremia gangetica</i>
<i>Kasamardaka</i>	<i>Cassia occidentalis</i>	<i>Kshavaka</i>	<i>Centipeda minima L.</i>
<i>Kapittapatri</i>	<i>Hesperethusa crenulata</i>	<i>Karmuka (rakta manjari)</i>	-
<i>Karmuka (atimuktaka)</i>	<i>Hiptage madablota Gaertn.</i>	<i>Kakamachi</i>	<i>Solanum americanum</i>
<i>Kulahala</i>	<i>Sphaeranthus indicus L.</i>	<i>Visamusti</i>	-
<i>Bhustrna</i>	<i>Cymbopogon citrates</i>	<i>Nirgundi</i>	<i>Vitex negundo L.</i>
<i>Phanijjaka</i>	-	<i>Katphala</i>	-
<i>Bharngi</i>	<i>Clerodendrum serratum(L)</i>	<i>Bhutakesi</i>	-

17). *Muskakadiganah*

Dravya of *Muskakadiganah* are useful for *Gulma, Meda, Ashmari, Pandu, Meda, Arsha, Sukrajita*. It has total of 7 Dravya. They are²³:

Table No. (19) List of Dravya described in *Muskakadiganah*

Sanskrit name	Latin / English name	Sanskrit name	Latin / English name
<i>Muskaka</i>	<i>Schrebera swietenoides Roxb.</i>	<i>Snuhi</i>	<i>Euphorbia neriifolia L.</i>

<i>Aamlaki</i>	<i>Phyllanthus emblica</i>	<i>Dvipi</i>	<i>Plumbago zeylanica</i>
<i>Palash</i>	<i>Butea monosperma</i>	<i>Dhava</i>	-
<i>Simashapa</i>	-		

18). *Vatsakadiganah*

Dravya of *Vatsakadiganah* are useful for *Pinasa*, *Gulma*, *Jwar*, *Shula*. It has total of 23 *Dravya*. They are²⁴:

Table No. (20) List of *Dravya* described in *Vatsakadiganah*

Sanskrit name	Latin / English name	Sanskrit name	Latin / English name
<i>Kutaja</i>	<i>Holarrhena antidysenterica</i> L.	<i>Ativisa</i>	<i>Aconitum heterophyllum</i>
<i>Aralu</i>	<i>Ailanthus excelsa</i>	<i>Yavani</i>	<i>Trachyspermum ammi</i> L.
<i>Sukalavaca</i>	<i>Acorus calamus</i>	<i>Suklavaca</i>	<i>Paris polyphylla</i>
<i>Murva</i>	<i>Marsdenia tenacissima</i>	<i>Bharngi</i>	<i>Clerodendrum serratum</i> (L)
<i>Katuka</i>	<i>Picrorhiza kurroo</i>	<i>Maricha</i>	<i>Piper nigrum</i> L.
<i>Gandira</i>	-	<i>Ela</i>	<i>Elettaria cardamomum</i> (L.)
<i>Patha</i>	<i>Cuminum cyminum</i> L.	<i>Ajaji</i>	-
<i>Pusagandha</i>	-	<i>Siddhartha</i>	-
<i>Jiraka</i>	<i>Cuminum cyminum</i> L.	<i>Hingu</i>	<i>Ferula narthex</i> Boiss
<i>Vidanga</i>	<i>Embelia ribes</i>		

19). *Vachadiganah*

Dravya of *Vachadiganah* are useful for *Aamatisara*, *Stanyadosha*, *Medaroga*, *Kapharoga*. It has total of 6 *Dravya*. They are²⁵:

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Table No. (21) List of Dravya described in *Vacadiganah*

Sanskrit name	Latin / English name	Sanskrit name	Latin / English name
<i>Vacha</i>	<i>Acorus calamus</i>	<i>Devahva</i>	<i>Cedrus deodara</i>
<i>Nagara</i>	<i>Zingiber officinale</i>	<i>Ativisa</i>	<i>Aconitum heterophyllum</i>
<i>Musta</i>	<i>Cyperus rotundus</i>	<i>Abhaya</i>	<i>Terminalia chebula</i>

20). Haridradiganah

Dravya of **Haridradi** re useful for *Aamatisara, Stanyadosha, Medaroga, Kapharoga*. It has total of 5 Dravya. They are²⁶:

Table No. (22) List of Dravya described in *Haridradiganah*

Sanskrit name	Latin / English name	Sanskrit name	Latin / English name
<i>Haridra</i>	<i>Curcuma longa L.</i>	<i>Daruharida</i>	<i>Berberis aristata</i>
<i>Yastyahva</i>	-	<i>Kalasi</i>	-
<i>Kutajodbhava</i>	-		

21). Priyangvadiganah

Dravya of **Priyangvadiganah** are useful for *Pakva atisara, Pittaroga, Vrana Ropana*. It has total of 14 Dravya. They are²⁷:

Table No. (23) List of Dravya described in *Priyangvadiganah*

Sanskrit name	Latin / English name	Sanskrit name	Latin / English name
<i>Priyangu</i>	<i>Callicarpa macrophylla</i>	<i>Puspanjana</i>	-

<i>Anjanayugma</i>		<i>Srotonjana</i>	-
<i>Sauviranjana</i>	-	<i>Padma</i>	<i>Nelumbo nucifera</i>
<i>Padmaraja</i>	-	<i>Yojanavalli</i>	<i>Rubia cordifolia</i>
<i>Ananta</i>	<i>Alhagi pseudalhagi</i>	<i>Manadruma</i>	<i>Bombax ceiba</i>
<i>Mocharasa</i>	<i>Bombax ceiba</i>	<i>Samanga</i>	<i>Mimosa pudica</i>
<i>Punnaga</i>	<i>Calophyllum inophyllum</i>	<i>Sita</i> (<i>Chandana</i>)	<i>Santalum album</i>
<i>Madaniyahetu</i>	<i>Woodfordia fruticosa</i>		

22). *Ambasthadiganah* :

Dravya of *Ambasthadiganah* are useful for *Pakva atisara*, *Pittaroga*, *Vrana Ropana*. It has total of 11 *Dravya*. They are²⁸:

Table No. (24) List of *Dravya* described in *Ambasthadiganah*:

Sanskrit name	Latin / English name	Sanskrit name	Latin / English name
<i>Ambastha</i>	<i>Actinopteris radiata</i>	<i>Madhuka</i>	<i>Glycyrrhiza glabra</i>
<i>Namaskari</i>	-	<i>Nandivrksha</i>	<i>Ficus retusa</i>
<i>Palasa</i>	<i>Butea monosperma</i>	<i>Kacchura</i>	-
<i>Rodhra</i>	<i>Symplocos recemosa</i>	<i>Dhataki</i>	<i>Woodfordia fruticosa</i>
<i>Bilvapesika</i>	-	<i>Katvanga</i>	-
<i>Kamalodbhavaraja</i>	-		

23). Mustadiganah

Dravya of *Mustadiganah* are useful for *Yoni-Stanya Roga*, *Malapachana*. It has total of 16 *Dravya*. They are²⁹:

Table No. (25) List of *Dravya* described in *Mustadiganah* :

Sanskrit name	Latin / English name	Sanskrit name	Latin / English name
<i>Musta</i>	<i>Cyperus rotundus</i>	<i>Katuka</i>	<i>Picrorhiza kurroa</i>
<i>Bhallataka</i>	<i>Samecarpus anacardium L.f.</i>	<i>Kustha</i>	<i>Saussurea costus</i>
<i>Vacha</i>	<i>Acorus calamus Linn.</i>	<i>Agni</i>	<i>Plumbago zeylanica</i>
<i>Haridra</i>	<i>Curcuma longa</i>	<i>Daruharidra</i>	<i>Berberis aristata</i>
<i>Ela</i>	<i>Elettaria cardamomum</i>	<i>Kakatikta</i>	-
<i>Svetavacha</i>	-	<i>Patha</i>	<i>Cissampelos pareira</i>
<i>Amlaki</i>	<i>Phyllanthus emblica</i>	<i>Haritaki</i>	<i>Terminalia chebula</i>
<i>Bibhitaki</i>	<i>Terminalia bellirica</i>	<i>Suklakanda</i>	-

24). Nyagrodhadiganah

Dravya of *Nyagrodhadiganah* are useful for *Vrana*, *Sangrahi*, *Bhagna*, *Yoniroga*, *Trushna*, *Medoroga*. It has total of 21 *Dravya*. They are³⁰:

Table No. (26) List of *Dravya* described in *Nyagrodhadiganah*:

Sanskrit name	Latin / English name	Sanskrit name	Latin / English name
<i>Nyagrodha</i>	<i>Ficus benghalensis</i>	<i>Pippala</i>	<i>Ficus religiosa</i>
<i>Sadaphala</i>	<i>Ficus racemosa</i>	<i>Lodhra</i>	<i>Symplocos recemosa</i>

<i>Sabaralodhra</i>	-	<i>Rajajambu</i>	<i>Syzygium cumini</i>
<i>Kakajambu</i>	<i>Syzygium salicifolium</i>	<i>Arjuna</i>	<i>Terminalia arjuna</i>
<i>Kapitana</i>	<i>Ficus arnottiana</i>	<i>Somavalka</i>	-
<i>Plaksa</i>	<i>Ficus lacor</i>	<i>Amra</i>	<i>Magnifera indica</i>
<i>Vanjula</i>	<i>Salix caprea</i>	<i>Piyala</i>	<i>Buchanania cochinchinensis</i>
<i>Palash</i>	<i>Butea monosperma</i>	<i>Nandivrksa</i>	-
<i>Koli</i>	<i>Ziziphus oenoplia</i>	<i>Kadamba</i>	-
<i>Virala</i>	<i>Diospyros malabarica</i>	<i>Madhuka</i>	<i>Glycyrrhiza glabra</i>
<i>Madhuka</i>	<i>Glycyrrhiza glabra</i>		

25). *Eladiganah*:

Dravya of *Eladiganah* are useful for *Vatakapharoga*, *Visha*, *Vranaprasadan*, *Knadu*, *Pitika*, *Kotha* It has total of 25 *Dravya*. They are³¹:

Table No. (27) List of *Dravya* described in *Eladiganah*:

Sanskrit name	Latin / English name	Sanskrit name	Latin / English name
<i>Suksmaila</i>	<i>Elettaria cardamomum</i>	<i>Turuska</i>	<i>Liquidambar orientalis</i>
<i>Kushta</i>	<i>Saussura lappa</i>	<i>Phalini</i>	-
<i>Mamsi</i>	-	<i>Jala</i>	<i>Pavonia odorata Willd.</i>
<i>Dhyamaka</i>	<i>Anisomeles malabarica</i>	<i>Sprukka</i>	-
<i>Choraka</i>	<i>Angelica glauca</i>	<i>Coca</i>	<i>Cinnamomum verum</i>
<i>Patra</i>	<i>Cinnamomum tamala Nees</i>	<i>Tagara</i>	<i>Valeriana jatamamsi Jones</i>

<i>Shauneya</i>	<i>Taxus wallichiana Zucc.</i>	<i>Jatirasa</i>	<i>Commiphora myrrha (Nees)</i>
<i>Sukti</i>	-	<i>Vyaghranakha</i>	-
<i>Amarahva</i>	-	<i>Agaru</i>	<i>Aquilaria malaccensis</i>
<i>Srivasaka</i>	-	<i>Kunkuma</i>	<i>Crocus sativus L.</i>
<i>Chanda</i>	<i>Angelica archangelica</i>	<i>Guggulu</i>	<i>Commiphora mukul Engl.</i>
<i>Devadhupa</i>	-	<i>Khapura</i>	-
<i>Punnaga</i>	-	<i>Nagahva</i>	-
<i>Brhadela</i>	<i>Amomum subulatum Roxb.</i>		

26). *Syamadiganah*

Dravyas of ***Syamadiganah*** are useful for *Gulma, Visha, Aruchi, Hrdaroga, Mutrakruhcha*. It has total of 20 *Dravya*. They are³²:

Table No. (28) List of *Dravya* described in *Syamadiganah*:

Sanskrit name	Latin / English name	Sanskrit name	Latin / English name
<i>Syama</i>	<i>Operculina turpethum</i>	<i>Danti</i>	<i>Baliospermum solanifolium</i>
<i>Dravanti</i>	-	<i>Kramuka</i>	-
<i>Kutarana</i>	<i>Merremia peltata</i>	<i>Sankhini</i>	<i>Ctenolepis cerasifoemis</i>
<i>Satala</i>	<i>Euphorbia Pilosa L.</i>	<i>Brahmi</i>	<i>Bacopa monnieri</i>
<i>Svarnaksiri</i>	<i>Euphorbia thomsoniana</i>	<i>Gavadani</i>	<i>Clitoria ternatea</i>
<i>Indravaruni</i>	<i>Citrullus colocynthis L.</i>	<i>Tilvaka</i>	<i>Viburnum nervosum</i>
<i>Kampilla</i>	<i>Mallotus philippensis</i>	<i>Guduchi</i>	<i>Tinosperma cordifolia</i>

<i>Karanja</i>	<i>Millettia pinnata</i>	<i>Bashtantri</i>	-
<i>Vyadhighata</i>	<i>Cassia fistula</i>	<i>Bahala</i>	<i>Moringa oleifera</i>
<i>Bahurasa</i>	<i>Saccharum officinarum</i>	<i>Tiksnavrksaphala</i>	<i>Salvadora india</i>

27). *Viprakirnadravyani*

The synonyms of the scattered medicinal plants are described here³³.

Table No. (29) List of Dravya described in *Viprakirnadravyani*:

Sanskrit name	Latin / English name	Sanskrit name	Latin / English name
<i>Sami</i>	<i>Prosopis cineraria</i>	<i>Aparajita</i>	<i>Clitoria ternatea</i>
<i>Paniya</i>	-	<i>Sankhapuspika</i>	<i>Convolvulus pluricaulis</i>
<i>Sarpaksi</i>	<i>Ophiorrhiza mungo L.</i>	<i>Nakuli</i>	<i>Aristolochia indica</i>
<i>Visnukranta</i>	<i>Evolvulus alsinoides(L.)</i>	<i>Bala</i>	<i>Sida cordifolia L.</i>
<i>Mahabala</i>	<i>Sida rhombifolia</i>	<i>Atibala</i>	<i>Abutilon indicum</i>
<i>Karpasa</i>	<i>Gossypium herbaceum</i>	<i>Tamalaki</i>	<i>Phyllanthus urinaria L.</i>
<i>Parpata</i>	<i>Fumaria indica</i>	<i>Trayamana</i>	<i>Gentiana kurroo</i>
<i>Duralabha</i>	<i>Fagonia arabica</i>	<i>Jalajambu</i>	<i>Syzygium salicifolium</i>
<i>Mahakadamba</i>	-	<i>Kinkirata</i>	<i>Acacia horrida</i>
<i>Parijata</i>	<i>Erythrina variegata</i>	<i>Sukanasa</i>	-
<i>Sakhota</i>	<i>Streblus asper</i>	<i>Kakodumbara</i>	<i>Ficus hispida L.</i>
<i>Vasa</i>	<i>Adhatoda zeylanica</i>	<i>Asmantaka</i>	<i>Bauhinia racemosa</i>
<i>Vansa</i>	<i>Bambusa bambos</i>	<i>Kumbhi</i>	<i>Careya arborea Roxb.</i>
<i>Sinduvara</i>	-	<i>Rohita</i>	-

<i>Phalgu</i>	<i>Ficus carica</i>	<i>Khadiravalli</i>	-
<i>Vatapatrika</i>	-	<i>Phenila</i>	<i>Ziziphus jujuba Lam.</i>
<i>Sara</i>	<i>Saaccharum bengalense</i>	<i>Slesmantaka</i>	<i>Cordia myxa Roxb.</i>
<i>Kovidara</i>	<i>Bauhinia purpurea</i>	<i>Asvagandhika</i>	<i>Withnia somnifera</i>
<i>Badara</i>	<i>Ziziphus sativa</i>	<i>Vrksamla</i>	<i>Garcinia indica</i>
<i>Karkandhu</i>	<i>Zizyphus nummularia</i>	<i>Dhanvana</i>	<i>Grewia tilifolia Vahl.</i>
<i>Amlavetasa</i>	<i>Garcinia pedunculata</i>	<i>Godhapadi</i>	-
<i>Adityavalli</i>	-	<i>Vrddhadaruka</i>	<i>Argyreia nervosa</i>
<i>Ksudrakantarika</i>	<i>Solanum trilobatum L.</i>	<i>Raktaganja</i>	<i>Abrus precatorius</i>
<i>Svetaganja</i>	<i>Abrus fruticosus</i>	<i>Krsnaganja</i>	-
<i>Jyotishmati</i>	<i>Celastrus paniculatus</i>	<i>Isvari</i>	<i>Aristolochia indica</i>
<i>Adhahpuspi</i>	<i>Trichodesma zeylanicum</i>	<i>Varahi</i>	<i>Dioscorea bulbifera L.</i>
<i>Aramasitala</i>	-	<i>Nagajihva</i>	<i>Holostemma ada-kodien</i>
<i>Nimbacchada</i>	<i>Momordica dioica</i>	<i>Likhika</i>	-
<i>Badarikaparni</i>	-	<i>Bakuci</i>	<i>Psoralea corylifolia</i>
<i>Aranyakulattha</i>	<i>Cassia absus L.</i>	<i>Haridru</i>	<i>Haldina cordifolia</i>
<i>Arimeda</i>	<i>Acacia farnesiana L.</i>	<i>Tiksnasara</i>	-
<i>Pauskara</i>	<i>Inula racemosa Hook.</i>	<i>Sati</i>	<i>Hedychium spicatum</i>
<i>Durva</i>	<i>Cynodon dactylon</i>	<i>Aghotaka</i>	-
<i>Ajaksi</i>	-	<i>Bhrngaraja</i>	<i>Eclipta alba L.</i>
<i>Suryabhakta</i>	-		

Table No.30: Dravya described into Saka Varga

<i>Masuli</i>	<i>Kumbhi</i>	<i>Aksoda</i>	<i>Agasti</i>	<i>Tanduliya</i>	<i>Cilli</i>
<i>Kandeksu</i>	<i>Kasa</i>	<i>Dronapuspi</i>	<i>Kaundinya</i>	<i>Sunisannaka</i>	<i>Matsyaksi</i>
<i>Kokilaksa</i>	<i>Uccata</i>	<i>Adhicchatra</i>	<i>Cakrangi</i>	<i>Vastuka</i>	<i>Sravani</i>
<i>Dhattura</i>	<i>Devadali</i>	<i>Prapunnata</i>	<i>Laksmna</i>	<i>Barbarika</i>	<i>Chatraka</i>
<i>Kosatakidvaya</i>	<i>Alabu</i>	<i>Nagavalli</i>	<i>Vajravalli</i>	<i>Palandu</i>	<i>Satapuspa</i>
<i>Nilini</i>	<i>Tamracuda</i>	<i>Palankasa</i>	<i>Dadhipuspi</i>	<i>Misreya</i>	<i>Prthvika</i>
<i>Gojihva</i>	<i>Ankola</i>	<i>Bimbi</i>	<i>Urvaru</i>	<i>Kapittha</i>	<i>Kumbhi</i>
	<i>Bakula</i>	<i>Sanapuspi</i>	<i>Kalinga</i>	<i>Trapusa</i>	
	<i>Atasi</i>	<i>Brahmi</i>	<i>Kusmandaki</i>	<i>Goraksatumbi</i>	
	<i>Mandukaparni</i>	<i>Putrajiva</i>	<i>Cirbhata</i>	<i>Tumbika</i>	
	<i>Avarttiki</i>	<i>Prasarani</i>	<i>Tintidi</i>	<i>Cangeri</i>	
	<i>Hingupatri</i>	<i>Tumburu</i>	<i>Upodaki</i>	<i>Kalambi</i>	

Table No.31: Dravya described into Phala Varga

<i>Narikela</i>	<i>Kadaliphala</i>	<i>Turyatundi</i>	<i>Kitahantri</i>
<i>Kadali</i>	<i>Karamardi</i>	<i>Kumari</i>	<i>Bandhuka</i>
<i>Karamardaka</i>	<i>Matulunga</i>	<i>Kaidarya</i>	<i>Visvarupa</i>
<i>Jambira</i>	<i>Naranga</i>	<i>Surana</i>	<i>Raktapadi</i>
<i>Bhavya</i>	<i>Likuca</i>	<i>Kharjuri</i>	<i>Hintali</i>
<i>Panasa</i>	<i>Nalika</i>	<i>Jantuvrksa</i>	<i>Nilini</i>
<i>Plaksa</i>	<i>Kuberkasi</i>	<i>Kakajangha</i>	<i>Sarapunkha</i>

<i>Karavalli</i>	<i>Pancanguli</i>	<i>Putradatri</i>	<i>Talisa</i>
<i>Vikantaka</i>	<i>Kubjapuspa</i>		

Table No.32: Dravya described into Parthiva Dravya

<i>Khatika</i>	<i>Gairika</i>
<i>Dugdhapasana</i>	<i>Gandhaka</i>
<i>Manahsila</i>	<i>Haritala</i>
<i>Parada</i>	<i>Abhraka</i>
<i>Karparituttha</i>	<i>Hingula</i>
<i>Sindura</i>	

Table No.33: Dravya described into Lavana and Kshara

<i>Sauvarcalavana</i>	<i>Samudralavana</i>
<i>Audbhidavana</i>	<i>Tankanaksara</i>
<i>Svarjikaksara</i>	<i>Silajatu</i>
<i>Maksika</i>	<i>Laksa alaktaka</i>
<i>Saurastri</i>	<i>Samudralavana</i>

Table No.34: Dravya described into Jantava Dravyas

<i>Kasturi</i>	<i>Latakasturika</i>
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Table No.35: Dravya described into Gandha Dravya

<i>Karpura</i>	<i>Marjarakasturi</i>
<i>Jatipatri</i>	<i>Kakkolaka</i>
<i>Lavanga</i>	<i>Silapuspa</i>
<i>Puspanjana</i>	

Table No.36: Dravya described into Dhatu

<i>Samudraphena</i>	<i>Tiksnaloha</i>
<i>Sankha</i>	<i>Pravala</i>
<i>Rajata</i>	<i>Suvarna</i>

<i>Tamra</i>	<i>Pittala</i>
<i>Trapu</i>	<i>Kamsya</i>
<i>Varttaloha</i>	<i>Krsnaloha</i>
<i>Lohakitta</i>	<i>Baluka</i>
<i>Ayaskanta</i>	

Synonyms described into Visa dravya

Kalukuta, Mahamusta, Vatsanabha, Halahala, Vatsadanti, Mahasrngi, Leliha, Talapatraka, Visa, Mulaka, Srngi, Gara, and Krtrimasanjnaka are the synonyms of visa.

Table No.37: Dravya described into Jaliya dravyas

<i>Jalakumbhika</i>	<i>Pankaja</i>
<i>Saivala</i>	<i>Kakotpala</i>
<i>Kumuda</i>	<i>Srngatakaa</i>
<i>Kaseruka</i>	

Table No.38: Dravya described into Puspa Varga

<i>Karavira</i>	<i>Bakula</i>
<i>Tamrapuspi</i>	<i>Vanamalika</i>
<i>Amlayana</i>	<i>Tilaka</i>
<i>Malati</i>	<i>Mallika</i>
<i>Kubjaka</i>	<i>Sankhayuthika</i>
<i>Damanaka</i>	

Table No.39: Dravya described into Dravya Varga

<i>Jala</i>	<i>Ghrtalaya</i>
<i>Dugdha</i>	<i>Santana</i>
<i>Takra</i>	

Table No.40: Dravya described into IksuVarga and Madhu Varga

<i>Khanda</i>	<i>Sita</i>
<i>Madhu</i>	<i>Sikthaka</i>

Synonyms described into Taila Dravya

Taila, Abhyanjanavara, Tilaja and Tilasambhava are the synonyms of Taila.

Table No.41: Dravya described into Madya Varga

<i>Madya</i>	<i>Kanjika</i>
<i>Maireya</i>	<i>Suktakanjika</i>
<i>Mardvika</i>	<i>Gauda</i>
<i>Sarkara</i>	<i>Aiksava</i>
<i>Khandavasa</i>	<i>Paistaka</i>

Table No.42: Dravya described into Dhanya Varga

<i>Sali</i>	<i>Godhuma</i>
<i>Nivara</i>	<i>Priyangu</i>
<i>Kodrava</i>	<i>Jurna</i>
<i>Gavedhuka</i>	<i>Makustha</i>
<i>Krsnamudga</i>	<i>Canaka</i>
<i>Masura</i>	<i>Masa</i>
<i>Kulattha</i>	<i>Kalaya</i>
<i>Rajamasa</i>	<i>Nispava</i>
<i>Adhaki</i>	<i>Tila</i>
<i>Yava</i>	

Table No.43: Dravya described into Misra Varga

<i>triphala</i>	<i>Trikatu</i>
<i>Dasamula</i>	<i>Trijataka</i>
<i>Panchkola</i>	<i>Ausadha</i>

Table No.44: Dravya described into Mamsa Varga

<i>Gardabha</i>	<i>Sardula</i>	<i>Chuchundari</i>	<i>Bidala</i>
<i>Ustra</i>	<i>Mrga</i>	<i>Godha</i>	<i>Gundupada</i>
<i>Simla</i>	<i>Vanara</i>	<i>Pipilaka</i>	<i>Madhumaksika</i>
<i>Sukra</i>	<i>Paravata</i>	<i>Madhukara</i>	<i>Damsa</i>
<i>Srgala</i>	<i>Mayura</i>	<i>Puttika</i>	<i>Khadyota</i>
<i>Kukkuta</i>	<i>Kaka</i>	<i>Bhrngari</i>	<i>Gavaya</i>
<i>Uluku</i>	<i>Carmapathika</i>	<i>Mahisa</i>	<i>Grsti</i>
<i>Cataka</i>	<i>Cataka</i>	<i>Balivarda</i>	<i>Baskayani</i>
<i>Bharadvaja</i>	<i>Kacchapa</i>	<i>Manduka</i>	<i>Nakula</i>
<i>Kokila</i>	<i>Sambuka</i>	<i>Sarata</i>	<i>Musaka</i>
<i>Karkata</i>	<i>Jalauka</i>	<i>Nalini</i>	<i>Grhagodhika</i>
<i>Mina</i>	<i>Sarpa</i>		

Table No.45: Dravya described into Sarira dhatu and Dosas

<i>S</i>	<i>Rakta</i>
<i>Mamsa</i>	<i>Mamsa</i>

<i>Asthi</i>	<i>Virya</i>
<i>Vata</i>	<i>Kapha</i>

Table No.46: Dravya described into Earth and Planets

<i>Mrttika</i>	<i>Pasana</i>
<i>Kutu</i>	<i>Ravi</i>
<i>Prthivi</i>	<i>Budha</i>
<i>Candra</i>	<i>Ketu</i>
<i>Sukra</i>	<i>Nisa</i>
<i>Naksatra</i>	<i>Divasa</i>

Table No.47: Dravya described into Gods and Goddesses

<i>Siva</i>	<i>Visnu</i>
<i>Parvati</i>	<i>Mulu</i>
<i>Laksmi</i>	<i>Sikhara</i>
<i>Sikhara</i>	

Table No.48: Dravya described into Parts of plants

<i>Patra</i>	<i>Phala</i>
<i>Kali</i>	<i>Puspa</i>

Table No.49: Dravya described into Medicine and physician

<i>Ausadha</i>
<i>Kriya</i>
<i>Vaidya</i>

Conclusion:

Astanga Nighantu is a work of 8th century A.D. There is a total of 26 Varga, first Varga is Dravyas of 26 Gana of Vagbhata. Then Viprakirnadavyani Varga, Synonyms of the scattered medicinal plants are described here And Synonyms of Dravya which included in Saka Varga, Phala Varga, Lavana, Ksara, Parthiv Dravya, Jantava Dravya, Gandha Dravya, Dhatu, Visa, Jaliya Dravya, Puspa Dravya, IksuVarga, Madhu Varga, Dhanya Varga etc. are described here. *Astanga Nighantu* comprises of synonyms of the Dravya. The author had made attempts to describe the drugs clearly and as such he has coined new synonyms which are very significant for giving clear picture of Dravya Eg.: Phanijhvaparni for Satavari, Vindhayata for Bibhitaki, Pittasara for Bijaka, Mandalpatrak for Sinsipa, Kantakikinshuk for Paribhadra³⁴. Latin or English name of dravya of various Varga are written here is taken from *Astanga Nighantu* (Editor and Commentator by Acharya Balkrishna, Divya Prakashan, Haridwar, 2019). Latin or English name of Dravyas are not written here, as it is not mention in *Astanga Nighantu* (Editor and Commentator by Acharya Balkrishna, Divya Prakashan, Haridwar, 2019).

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